

Pope St. John Paul II's Understanding of Suffering and Its Impact in the Concept of Martyrdom

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Abstract

Pope St. John Paul II, in his famous Apostolic letter *Salvifici Doloris* speaks about Christ's active participation in the suffering of humanity and the redemptive aspect of human suffering. When speaking about human suffering, he transcends the philosophical approach and speaks from his own personal experience and applies it to the paschal mystery of Jesus Christ. God's revelation in Christ is paradoxical because Christ reveals himself through the experience of suffering, weakness, and death. We see a frightened, abandoned person suffering in the Garden of Gethsemane perspiring blood, pleading pathetically for help. He suffers through untold humiliation, torture, betrayal, and finally painful death on the cross. This new image of God shatters all-powerful, all-knowing, and all-loving traditional image transmitted from generation to generation. This new image of God gives a new understanding of God, which is a shift from the traditional, transcendental God of biblical image. Since Jesus the real image of Father who himself suffered, wishes to answer to the human suffering from the Cross, from the heart of his own suffering.

Introduction

The human being for many centuries has been contemplating the perplexing problem of human suffering to arrive at an acceptable answer. At times for the people who go through suffering throughout the phases of their entire life. There is no escape from the questions of 'Why?' and 'What for?' Even though suffering is a universal reality, there is no single explanation of the cause or the purpose of it. Throughout Christian history, several explanations were put forward by deep thinkers on the reality of suffering. Some theologians have claimed that human suffering is the starting point of theology and many agree that suffering is an enormous theological theme that is not easy to answer. Yet there is a concept of 'theology of suffering' in the teaching of Pope St. John Paul II who says, "We can indeed find meaning in suffering provided we look for it in the treasury of divine

wisdom fully revealed in Jesus Christ, because only in Jesus the mystery of sorrow and death grow meaningful” (John Paul II, (1984), VIII: 31).

His reflection on ‘theology of suffering’ fascinates more than his other teachings because he speaks from his own experience. He lost his mother and brother early in his life and later his father too. During the second world war as a young man, he experienced starvation and suffering, torture, and mass murder were not new to him. The suffering continued in his pontificate until his death but never gave up his faith, holding the crucifixion of Christ tight and close to his heart, he withstood all the ailing, man of great faith. I believe that his teaching about the theology of suffering is an inspiration and a good insight for all the people who are suffering in this world due to various reasons.

Theology of Suffering

Pope St. John Paul II, in his famous spiritual teachings, speaks about Christ’s active participation in the suffering of humanity and the redemptive aspect of human suffering. When speaking about human suffering, he transcends the theoretical and philosophical approach and speaks from his own personal experience, and applies it to the biblical, historical, and paschal mystery of Jesus Christ. God’s revelation in Christ is paradoxical because Christ reveals himself through the experience of suffering, weakness, and death; We see a scared, frightened, abandoned person suffering in the Garden of Gethsemane perspiring blood, pleading pathetically for help. He suffers through untold humiliation, torture, treason, and finally painful death on the cross. This new image of God shatters all-powerful, all-knowing, and all-loving traditional images transmitted from generation to generation. This new image of God gives a new understanding of God, which is a shift from the traditional, transcendental God of biblical image. Jesus, the real image of Father who himself suffered, wishes to answer to the human suffering from the Cross, from the heart of his own suffering (John Paul II, (1984), V: 26).

Jesus was not a stranger to suffering during his public ministry, but he never mentioned the ‘theology of suffering’ though his whole life was with the suffering people. He healed, consoled, and comforted the suffering humanity; He himself experienced loneliness, fatigue, and humiliation finally death on the Cross. This is God’s contribution to the solidarity of suffering of humanity. Pope St. John Paul II in his spiritual meditation has not placed suffering on a philosophical or ideological basis, but with Christ who experienced human suffering and became the answer for suffering (Patrick Boyle, (2003), 101). According to the teaching of the Catholic Church salvation means participating in the divine life of Christ who came down from heaven and shares with us. Because Jesus is human, he can be

one of us, but because he is also divine, he can make us all divine, sharers of the divine life. Thus, Christ is the center of our redemption which is called Christocentric (Michael Amalados, (2006), 17).

Meaning of Martyrdom

The word Martyrdom in English has its root in Greek ‘Martyr’ (μάρτυρ), which means ‘witnessing’ or being a witness. The word ‘martyr’ was used by Aristotle and Plato to mean ‘witnessing to the truth’ whether it was orally transmitted truth, or the values proclaimed in religious books. The word martyr in Greek meant the personal experience one encounters in his life or the truth that learned or received from a particular person (Henk A, Bakker, (2015), 391-394). Witnessing oneself does not always mean that it leads the person to death. However, in most circumstances, those who witness the truth were led to a situation of embracing death. Therefore, those who witnessed to the truth for higher motives and for their religious beliefs were put to death by those who considered them as opposing. Those who died in this manner are considered ‘martyrs’ and the type of death that they embrace is called ‘martyrdom.’ Particularly in the Christian tradition the term ‘witnessing’ was used to identify those who were martyred for their faith (Mabel Quined, (1965), 659-660). In this background, the scripture mentions that at the beginning of Christianity, the apostles witnessed to what they had seen, heard, and directly experienced from Jesus during his earthly ministry (Acts 4:20).

Martyrdom in the New Testament

In the New Testament, the early Christians were subjected to suffering and death just because they accepted Jesus as Lord and openly confessed it. In this manner, those who shed their blood for Christ and sacrificed their lives were called martyrs by the Holy Church. Jesus was the central figure of Christianity, and Christians are called to follow and imitate Him, to live not just for themselves but commit their lives for others, and to have an attitude of obedience to the will of God. Proclaiming the Gospel is not a service of just empty words; but witnessing to Christ by life example is an important duty of every Christian. While proclaiming the Good News being preached in this manner, if Christians encountered death by shedding their blood for Christ, that witness became the source for the spreading of Christianity to many parts of the world. Added to that the Church, which is entrusted with the important duty of proclaiming the Gospel, becomes an example through such martyrdom to the love and trust in Christ (Fabrizio Meroni, (2019), 8). Jesus, the one considered the founder of Christianity is the first martyr for the sake of his faith in God, his higher motivation, and for the redemption of mankind, he sacrificed his

life. Similarly, those who follow him, sacrifice their life for the same higher motives as a gift, their action becomes martyrdom.

Martyrdom is proposed as a way of life and a witness for all those who are called to be disciples of Christ. Because Jesus Christ who founded Christianity was the first and greatest martyr on account of His crucifixion. He is an exemplar of Martyrdom, therefore a 'witnessing life' can be defined as a life of acceptance of Jesus through suffering and death. Jesus Christ, though he was equal to God, yet in obedience to God, the Father's command took the state of a slave accepted death on the cross and became a witness to God's love (Phil 2: 6-9). Because Jesus not only accepted death but by hanging on the cross, accepted the curse on himself as well, for the Scripture says that the one lets to hang on the tree is cursed by God (Gal 3:13). Thus, for the sake of his faith in God when someone accepts death, suffering and shame are accepted as contained implicitly within the term martyrdom.

The Theology of Martyrdom

Jesus calls people to Himself and demands from them a total commitment to Himself; Nothing of this world, not father or mother, husband or wife, son or daughter, or material goods, ought to stand between Him and His children. (Lk 14: 26) Jesus expects them to learn from Him and to become like Him. Then Jesus sends them into the world as His Father sent Him into the world, to spread His message and to be His witnesses. He knew that the world would hate His witnesses and would turn against them with merciless violence. Nonetheless, He expects them to meet that hatred with love, and to face that violence with glad acceptance, following His example by suffering and dying for the lost world. Their suffering and martyrdom are prompted by their faithfulness to Jesus and are endured for the purpose of spreading His gospel. Christ's disciples do not seek these things for their own sake, and they do not inflict these on themselves. Their goal is not to suffer and to die; on the contrary, their goal is to accomplish Christ's vision that is to establish the kingdom of God and spreading of His gospel.

The Theology of martyrdom is built on the experience of the death and resurrection of Jesus and got its vitality in the commitment of the martyrs, who sacrificed their lives in the ongoing religious persecution. The early Christians who wanted to be like Christ not only in life but also at death, came forward to sacrifice their lives. Therefore, the conviction of becoming a martyr is not just a sudden change of behavior, but a principle in life, took root in them in their daily life, and up to now has seen manifold growth. In the early church the faith understanding of martyrdom was not brought into awareness by the Fathers of the Church or bishops

and priests. Instead, it came into an acceptable existence, by the witnessing life of those who were taken up by the preaching of Jesus, as well as that of the apostles. Christianity has its base in the experience of God and in the Scriptures that came into existence through the God's experience for its theology. The experience of the Church, though has in its center in the historical event of birth, death, and resurrection of Jesus, this experience has the relationship of the people of Israel, and the covenant they made with God, gave the way for the development of Theology of Martyrdom. (G. F. Van Ackeren, (1966), 39-49)

Paschal Mystery of Christ

In Christian Theology, the term 'Paschal Mystery' refers to Jesus' passion, death and resurrection and their saving significance for us. Thus, paschal mystery is the ideal point to start our journey towards the Theology of Suffering. Because paschal mystery, apart from being the ultimate act of God's unconditional love towards humanity, it is God's response to the mystery of human suffering. Even though the Theology of Suffering seems to be Christocentric, there is no contradiction between Christocentricity and Theocentricity, for it was Jesus Christ who revealed the mystery of Trinity. Especially the suffering Jesus revealed his Father who is God, rich in Mercy, who forgives, and who is faithful. Pope explains that Jesus is the personification of unconditional love of the Father who was ready to suffer and to be crucified for the sake of humanity. (John Paul II, (1980), no 1) Second Vatican Council states that through Christ and in Christ the riddle sorrow and death become meaningful with Christ, because Christ is the starting point in understanding humanity and without Christ, man is incomprehensible. The Paschal mystery accomplishes the salvific mission for which Jesus came on earth. It became as the climax of revelation of God's love which is the central point of understanding the mystery of suffering. (Gaudium et Spes, (1965), no 22)

The suffering provides man an opportunity to open himself to Christ who gives a new vision of suffering through his paschal mystery. When suffering and sickness are lived in faith as a result, God reveals his strength through Christ and defeat the evil of suffering through his love. Writing to the Corinthians St. Paul says, "So, I will boast all the more gladly of my weaknesses, so that the power of Christ may dwell in me. Therefore, I am content with weaknesses, insults, hardships, persecutions, and calamities for the sake of Christ; for whenever I am weak, then I am strong." (2 Cor 12: 10) The remarkable truth is salvation of human being came through Jesus' passion and death and resurrection rather than, all his preaching, teaching, and performing miracles. (Ronald Rolheiser, (1989), 2)

In the paschal mystery, Christ is the summit of the revelation of the unfathomable mystery of God, and it accomplishes the salvific mission of Christ for which Jesus came on earth. (John Paul II, (1980), no 8) The Pontiff affirms that Jesus did not flee from the mystery of human suffering, rather he embraced the suffering, and in his passion, death, and resurrection, he opened a new way of hope and everlasting glory. (John Paul II, (1990), 413) The only true way to take part in Christ's triumph over sin and death is by uniting with him in his passion. The suffering invites each and every Christians to a life of sacrifice connected with Christ. In this way we could be totally conformed to the Cross of Christ.

Redemptive Act of Suffering

The New Testament speaks about redemption in much laudable manner especially John the evangelist makes praiseworthy contribution to the theology of redemption. He speaks of Jesus as "lamb of God who takes away the sin of the world." (Jn 1:29) In many passages in the letter of St. Paul we could gather promoting atonement model of redemption. He stresses firmly that Christ's passion and death is the process of making amends for the sin of the humanity against God the Creator. In the letter to Romans, St. Paul says, "God has done what the law, weakened by the flesh, could not do: by sending his own son in the likeness of sinful flesh, and to deal with sin, he condemned sin in the flesh." (Rom 8:3) According to St. John Paul II, the chief component in the theology of redemption is the suffering of the Son of God which is the ransom requirement to save humanity. The suffering in itself, is not redemptive, but it becomes redemptive because of the power of love of Christ which accompanied him to the suffering, death and finally to the resurrection. (Joseph Kimu, (2013), 143)

The Scripture had foretold this divine plan of salvation through the putting to death of 'the righteous one, my servant' as a mystery of universal redemption, that is as the ransom that would free men from the slavery of sin. The righteous one was Jesus Christ, and his death was the price that had to be paid to liberate men from the slavery of sin. In this way, the sin and disobedience of Adam and Eve were paid back by the love and filial obedience of Jesus Christ to his Father through embracing suffering on our behalf. (CCC, (1997), no 601) St. Paul professes that Christ died for our sins in accordance with the scripture. Particularly Jesus' redemptive death fulfils Isaiah's prophecy of the suffering servant, "But he was wounded for our transgressions, crushed for our iniquities; upon him was the punishment that made us whole, and by his bruises we are healed" (Isa 53:5).

The Jewish leaders were well versed in the prophecies and they dared to see Jesus whether he would rise to the challenge of suffering and death to prove the

prophecy. Jesus accepted the suffering as the consequence of his prophetic challenge. It was an explicit show of his commitment to truth and justice. For him, suffering is not a sign of weakness or surrender. It is a sign of courage and strength. A person who suffers and dies for a good cause should not attract our pity or sympathy or sorrow, but it provokes our admiration and appreciation. First, the sufferer himself undergoes psychological change process in understanding the self. Secondly, the people start looking at the sufferer not only as a victim but a hero- a living icon for the ultimate cause for what he is suffering. The people not only admire him but prepare themselves to take the path of struggle and suffering. Finally, it changes the people who are inflicting the pain and suffering on others. Thus, Jesus' suffering becomes transformative and redemptive of the others too. (Michael Amaladoss, (2006), 100) In the same way there were number of incidences in the life of martyrs when they were slaughtered and burnt alive for witnessing their faith in Christ, the executioners and nonbelievers had changed their heart and became Christians by seeing the glorious moment of martyrdom of Christians when they face the suffering and death with happiness and strong in their faith.

Cross Reveals the Love of God

Cross is a symbol that reveals the greatest love of God for humankind. When Jesus loudly cried and breathed his last, the curtain of the temple was torn in two, from top to bottom. (Mk 15: 37 -38) The curtain is actually a heavily decorated or plain screen that separated the worshipers from the sanctuary where the glory of glories is present. The torn curtain sheds light on the fact that the sin of the mankind does not exist any longer. The sin that prevented the man to have direct contact has been washed and peace is restored again. It was made possible by the love of Christ on the Cross. Christ on the Cross achieved what the high priests of the old Covenant had attempted to do on the day of atonement. For Hebrews, the tearing of the veil corresponds to the tearing of Christ's flesh. (Gordon J. Wenham, (1979), 237)

When the evangelist narrates that curtain of the temple was torn from the top to bottom, it means the love of Christ on the Cross removed the sins of humankind that prevented from seeing the inner heart of God. Thus, the Cross paved the way to all people of sinners to go into the new Jerusalem, the kingdom of God. The Cross of Jesus not only reveals God as unconditional love, but it also reveals how vulnerability is the path to intimacy with God. The Cross of Jesus teaches us more clearly than any other revelation that God is absolutely and utterly nonviolent. (Ronald Rolheiser, (2015), 36) We always connect God to intimidation, threat, guilt, reckoning and create an idea that God is powerful who will rise one

day or other to crush the evil. That is why many of us fear God, but disappoint in Him, saying that God is not doing anything against evil doers. In contrast to our idea, God is love and merciful, gentle in persistent, who is never a threat. God exists as an infinite patience that endures all things, not a great punisher like hero in movies who kills all the bad guys. So, the Cross of Jesus Christ reveals that God works far differently who never overpowers anyone. In fact, the Cross of Christ radiates the greatest love humanity has ever experienced, a love which gives humanity true freedom and introduces him to complete brotherhood with the rest of humanity. The Cross stands for faith and love and also bears testimony to the wonderful rescue plan God the Father had to redeem the world. (Joseph Kimu, (2013), 132)

Cross and Resurrection of Christ

Christianity draws its source and strength from the Cross of the Risen Jesus and the resurrection of the Crucified Christ. The Risen Christ is the same one who was crucified. Biblical theology clearly shows that there is an evident and irreplaceable interaction between Cross and Resurrection resulting that they are inseparable when Jesus appeared to Paul on the way to Damascus (Act 9: 3-8), and the biblical episode of St. Thomas touching wounds of Jesus clearly confirm that the Risen Christ is the same Jesus who suffered and died on the Cross (Jn 20: 26-29). Jesus on the Cross cries out his agony pleading his Father not to forsake him. At that moment God seemed to be absent or silent. Jesus' passion continues in a very high dramatic situation, thus the Son died completely forsaken and abandoned by his Father. However, His presence is heavily felt during the Resurrection of his Son. He transformed the Cross that was previously a sign of sin into a sign of sacrificial love and redemption. It is an eternal proof that the Cross and Resurrection cannot be divided. Otherwise, Jesus' passion on the Cross, Death and Resurrection will be of no value to our faith. Without the Resurrection, Jesus' magnificent story would be an ordinary episode among the numerous stories of pagan religion.

The intimate and inseparable bond between the Cross and Resurrection is stressed by a good number of theologians. Pontiff was an ardent believer in this intimacy and says that the suffering of Jesus already acquired glory which subsequently revealed in his Resurrection. (John Paul II, (1984), V: 22) Therefore, participants in Christ's suffering are entitled to share his glory.

Martyrdom and the Resurrection

St. Paul who understands the deep theological meaning of the death and resurrection of Jesus Christ, said that Jesus Christ showed the faith he had in God

by the way he lived his life on earth, and that faith led him to a glorified level of life through his resurrection. Not only the apostles, but also the early Church reflected that the resurrection of Christ happened as a consequence to the faith Christ had in God. Therefore, Paul confidently believed that all those who have faith in Christ will attain the glory of the resurrection and the God who made it possible for Christ to rise from the dead will also enable all to rise from their death and bring them in the presence of Christ. (2 Cor 4: 11-14)

Those who had deep faith in Jesus' resurrection, not only embraced Christianity, but also, as people who were aware that Christ's second coming (Parousia) was very close at hand, and with the intention of receiving the crown of victory, were prepared to face whatever obstacles or death in their lives. (Thomas P. Rausch, (2003), 127) St. Paul's epistles reveal that their conviction was made stronger by the preaching of the apostles and by their death by martyrdom. That is why he says, "...I have fought the good fight, I have finished the race, I have kept the faith. Now there is in store for me the crown of righteousness, which the Lord, the righteous Judge, will award to me on that day..." (2 Tim 4: 6-8) The faith in the resurrection, not only gave many the spiritual strength to endure sufferings and courage to face death but also helped them learn, that all the sufferings that they encounter in life have a salvific value. On the Cross, Jesus Christ's martyrdom was revealed, and by his resurrection, he received the crown of glory for his martyrdom. Similarly, Jesus' resurrection will reward everyone, who because of their faith in Him witnessing to Him. This Theology of Martyrdom which developed and grew in the early Church has not decreased but continues to be the seed and manure for the growth of the Church. (Joseph Ratzinger, (2011), 245-246) Thus early Christian apologist Tertullian says, "Blood of the martyrs is the seed of faith."

Christ's death on the Cross and the Resurrection are the two sides of the same coin or the two events of the same glorious event of Salvation. Our minds and hearts should be directed towards both aspects – the Cross of Jesus and the Risen Jesus. The book 'Christology at the Crossroad' by Jon Sobrino summarizes that Cross without the Resurrection leads to unbelief, despair and death of love. On the other hand, the Resurrection without the Cross leads to false confidence. (Jon Sobrino, (1978), 229)

Redeemed, but Still Suffering

The redemption of Christ does not grant us a special exception from pain, suffering and death, instead of that the Son of God underwent all the physical, moral suffering and death. In the Gospel of John, Chapter 11, verses 1 - 27 speak about Lazarus and his resurrection; Hearing that Jesus is coming, Martha went ahead of

him and asked, “Lord, if you had been here, my brother would not have died.” In fact, Martha’s question implies more; Why is that God invariably seems absent when bad things happen to good people? Why doesn’t God rescue his loved ones and save them from suffering and death? The answer to this question teaches us that our God is not a God who ordinarily rescues the people, rather than He is God who redeemed us. He doesn’t promise to erase all the suffering and death from the human history, rather He redeemed pain and death through his Son Jesus Christ on the Cross. Everyone has his own stories of suffering in this life. Such experiences present them with the tough reality that while the Cross saves us from eternal suffering, it doesn’t liberate us from the evil of earthly pain here and now. As Christians we struggle with this mystery bound up in our experience of God, who sometimes heals our suffering but in other circumstances seems silent. (Robert G. Schroeder, (2008), 113)

We believe that we have no better answer for this question than Jesus himself on the Cross. Jesus who is intimately loved by the Father and yet while he was hanging on the Cross, cried aloud to the Father, “My God, my God, why have you forsaken me?”(Mt 15:34) On the other side the crowd challenged him, “He trusts in God; let God deliver him now, if he wants to; for he said, ‘I am God’s Son.’” (Mt 27: 43) But there was no response from the heavenly Father. Instead, Jesus died in humiliation and pain. God raised him up only after his death. This is one of the key revelations inside the Cross, that our God is a redeeming God.

Conclusion

Suffering provides man an opportunity to open himself to Christ, who offers a new Christian vision of suffering through His paschal mystery. While suffering with Christ we enter into the innermost reality of the mystery of the redemption. At the same time, it is very important to make clear that Christians who live in situation of illness, pain and old age are called by God not only to unite their suffering to Christ’s passion but also to receive in themselves now, and to transmit to others the power of renewal and the joy of the risen Christ. (John Paul II, (1988), no 53) The Holy Father more explicitly says that the only way to share in Christ’s glorious victory over sin and death is by being united with Him in his passion. The passion of Christ invites each Christian to a life of sacrifice, in this way he becomes totally conformed to the Cross of Christ. Thus, Christians by virtue of their calling to follow the footsteps of their master Jesus Christ cannot be simply a spectator on Calvary but must participate in his master’s plight through offering their own suffering as an oblation of love. To understand the Divine revelation and the reality of life man needs the faith which is a gift from God through the Holy Spirit. Vatican

II says, “Faith is a decision involving one’s whole existence. It is an encounter, a dialogue, a communion of love and of life between the believer and Jesus Christ.” (Dei Verbum, (1965), no 5)

Christians understood that suffering is a redemptive factor and therefore they need not to be worrying to face it, because they no longer suffer alone but with Christ who is a friend, and the Father understands them in difficult situations. Pope says, that when there is an interior encounter between the suffering person and Christ, man spiritually unites himself to the Cross of Christ. This union leads the suffering person into happiness and peace amidst all his trials. (John Paul II, (1984), VI: 26) As the creation is moving towards its fullness, it faces birth, happiness, suffering and death on its path. It will not wither away because it has its inherent capacity to attain its fullness and man has the capacity to go beyond and transcend to reach the fullness in God. The suffering and death which came through the sin, was demolished and won by Christ through his sacrifice on the Cross. Hence, when man willfully unites his suffering with the suffering of Christ, he greatly contributes to this final victory of good over evil.

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